

! Aioli platform

The management of multi-dimensional and multi-format data for documenting cultural heritage artefacts induces new challenges, such as the development of relevant analysis and interpretation methods, the sharing and correlation of heterogeneous data among several actors and contexts, and the centralised archiving of documentation results for long-term preservation purposes.

Therefore, managing heterogeneous data raises the need for a stable denominator (from a conceptual and technical point of view) for structuring data and annotations coming from a continuous process of observation and analysis carried out by multiple actors.

What is the Aioli platform?

The Aioli platform is an innovative web service for the reality-based 3D annotation and large-scale collaborative documentation of heritage artefacts. The existing Aioli platform has been significantly upgraded in terms of technical robustness, the collaboration framework was provided, the management of controlled vocabularies and compatibility with CIDOC-CRM was established. A facility for visualising hypothetical reconstructions of archaeological sites was also added.

Key features

- ➔ The platform generates a dynamic 3D morphologic scaffolding for structuring data and annotations.
- ➔ This data structure becomes a way of enabling the communication between several actors involved in the documentation and the study of the same object.
- ➔ The platform interlinks all phases that characterise the overall documentation process within an “informative continuum”.
- ➔ It combines a continuous 3D mapping and annotation process, a morphology-based documentation framework and a flexible & scalable technology.
- ➔ The program combines the onsite retrieval of structured information according to the physical object’s annotation and the onsite collection and processing of new data to be spatially referenced and semantically correlated with previous data.

Benefits

- ➔ The interface for Aioli eases the collaborative work on shared projects, by adopting a social network-like approach for the user-end uses.
- ➔ The collaborative documentation of cultural heritage is accessible via web interfaces from PCs, tablets and smartphones online and onsite, because modern technological components were integrated within a cloud infrastructure.
- ➔ The platform integrates controlled vocabularies in SKOS Standard through the development of a portable and lightweight component for the visualization, search and term selection, linked to the thesaurus management software Opentheso.
- ➔ The definition of a mapping mechanism between the "Aioli" classes and attributes with the CIDOC CRM Ontology and CRM Digital compatible extension ensures full traceability of the Aioli "2D/3D collaborative annotation framework", the description of the photogrammetric process and heritage information.

More Information

- ➔ Report: [Specification of the new features of the Aioli platform](#)
- ➔ Presentation by De Luca, Livio. [Aioli a reality-based 3D annotation for the collaborative documentation of heritage artefacts.](#)

Who made the tool

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Access Aioli

[Presentation of the Aioli platform](#)

[SSHOC Service Catalogue](#)

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